

LINGUOPRAGMATIC ASPECT OF DISCURSIVE PERSONALITY

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ABSTRACT

Discourse analysis is considered in modern linguistics as central concepts. Discourse is a communicative, cultural, ethnic, psychological, emotional-expressive entity that embodies values and is composed in the form of unity and disunity, reflecting the speaker's communicative strategy through the relationship between speaker and listener, speech situation, and communicative-pragmatic-linguistic phenomena. In this article, the discussion and discursive personae are explored and some scholars' opinions on these terms are presented.

KEY WORDS: discourse, personae, pragmatics, pragmalinguistics, text.

Discourse theory demonstrates the integration of disciplines such as literary studies, linguistics, philosophy, history, sociology, anthropology, education, and political science with a high level of debate in the present era. It has become one of the central issues of discursive analysis, considered as a new direction in each of these fields with its own specific definition. In semiotics, discourse refers not only to a single utterance but also to a longer unity of language. The word "discourse" is derived from the Latin word "currere," which means "to run" in the sense of the prefix and "to move." Therefore, the term "migration" is translated and explains how a conversation progresses. Learning language is analyzing the use of spoken or written language in a social context. Discourse studies reveal the form and function of language in speech beyond its small grammatical parts, such as phonemes and morphemes. Discourse analysis in speech reveals the form and function of language in its small grammatical parts, such as phonemes and morphemes, beyond the Netherlands linguist Teun van Dijk has played an important role in the development of this research field, learning how language's larger units, including lexemes, syntax, and context, contribute meaning to conversations. Discourse is the social use of language for conveying broad historical meanings. The social conditions under which language is used, and the language in which it is used, are indicated. Language is never "neutral" because it serves to connect our personal and social worlds.

The concepts of functionality-structuralism, dynamic-static, actuality-virtuality are being used to differentiate phenomena at the basis of the notions

of "text" and "discourse." Michael Stubbs, who has been dealing with issues of text and discourse analysis for many years, stated in his work published in 1983: "People can distinguish a random sequence of words from a coherent text, therefore learning coherent ideas is the subject of discourse analysis".

From the last quarter of the 20th century, the need and attention to research any speech structure, which is a product of linguistic activity, from the point of view of the communication of the person who creates and perceives it - the author and the recipient - began to rise in world linguistics. One of the main factors that led to the emergence of the concept of discourse is the study of speech structure as a communication process. The word discourse, which was first used by the American linguist Zellig Harris in the 50s of the last century, means a phenomenon that represents one of the central issues of linguistics today. According to Ye.S. Kubryakova, "at the time of the current development of the science of linguistics, there is no generally accepted definition of discourse".

"Cognitive activity does not oppose creativity and perception, without their opposition, the cognitive process cannot take place. Therefore, one cannot agree with the opinion of H. Parret (Parret 1986) that "a language is the language of this community only when the discursive (speech) sequences of this language are understood by the members of this community". Better, I would recommend to change this description to "the members of a certain community can demonstrate the ability to understand a language and the ability to create through it, it becomes the language of this community" [1.67] says a well-known Uzbek. linguist Sh Safarov.

The fields of pragmatics and pragmalinguistics are closely related to understanding and cognitive linguistics. According to E.F.Tarasov, one of the linguists and psycholinguists who sought the methodological basis of pragmalinguistics from the theory of activity, we can understand in two ways that speech communication is closely related to human activity:

First, the activity determines the content and means of speech communication. The content of the dialogue consists of the cooperative activity of the communicants, and the choice of linguistic signs and the structure of the discourse (speech unit) meet the requirements of the purpose of this cooperation.

Secondly, the activity forms the world of objects in human imagination, and the existence of these objects is the first and main requirement of communication through signs. It is known that communication by means of

signs takes place only when the "world" of ideal objects of the communicants is common" (Tarasov 1989: 32).

Therefore, the adoption of the principle of activity as the basis of pragmalinguistic research made the analysis of the linguistic pragmatic content of the speech communication system a priority. This, in turn, further expanded the scope of pragmalinguistic research and encouraged to include in this scope all social phenomena related to the communication environment, in addition to the linguistic reality. A social event is, of course, an event that occurs between individuals, in which the individual is the basis. In this case, linguistic activity is considered as a type of relationship that occurs in the course of human socio-economic activity.

Despite the diversity of opinions regarding the definition of linguopragmatics, the description of its subject, we can say that the main ideas are the same:

- the basis of the description of communicative activity is the concept of activity;
- language is a tool that activates the interaction of the participants of the dialogue;
- the occurrence of linguistic activity is a phenomenon directly related to the communication environment (Aznaurova 1988:28).

All this can be the subject of research for separate areas of pragmalinguistics. For example, if the linguistic communication system is studied from the point of view of the subject of speech, attention is focused on phenomena such as the content of speech act types, the role of the communication goal in the discourse structure, the expression of the underlying meaning, presupposition, and the mental abilities of the participants (individuals) of communication. When the research is carried out from the point of view of the speech addressee, the main attention is focused on determining the pragmatic effect of the speech act. [1.75]

The existence of a language is closely related to the way people speak or write. In the process of performing these actions, linguistic units show the possibility of expressing content such as approval, command, warning, promise, in addition to their original meaning. These meanings are the result of speech activity performed by the speaker. Thus, we can say that a speech act is a linguistic appeal of the speaker to the listener in a certain environment and for a specific purpose.

Any linguistic activity requires a communicative environment, and linguistic communication, regardless of its form, is manifested in interpersonal relationships. Another phenomenon of the speech communication text that has a cognitive nature is the phenomenon of relevance. Psychologists Dan Sperber and Dyer Dre Wilson propose to consider this principle as a phenomenon that ensures the successful course of speech communication and the meaningful formation of a communication text. (Sperber, Wilson 1988).

Relevance or reliability is, first of all, a kind of meaningful coherence, which requires that the meaning of the speech act corresponds to the meaning of the actions preceding the text. Secondly, a certain speech structure should be suitable and appropriate for the communication environment and text, and only in this case the listener will understand the transmitted information quickly and easily. Therefore, the authors of the principle propose to measure the level of appropriateness by the achieved contextual result.

The terms "text" and "discourse" are not synonymous terms. Obviously, "discourse" is interpreted in a broader sense than "text". Yes, "discourse is both the process of linguistic activity and its product." Discursive activity is essentially the provision of knowledge (information) and "an event that forms new knowledge." In order to transmit and re-form knowledge, a text must be created. So, the text begins to be created at the moment of discursive activity. Discourse is a certain type and series of human conscious activity, and text is its manifestation.

In conclusion, it can be said that the basis of any linguistic discourse is the individual, and the understanding and explanation of the concept depends on the speaker and/or the listener.

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